

CH₄ (µg/g soil)

2. Effect of adding straw on CH₄ production 20 d after flooding. 1992 WS.

complex interaction of microbial metabolism of the whole fermentation chain and soil properties to determine mechanistically the CH₄ production potential of soils. ■

Predicting methane production in wetland rice soils

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Methane is an important greenhouse gas with a relative potential for thermal absorption 30 times greater than that of CO₂. It plays an important role in the chemistry of the troposphere. Methane production in soil is a microbiological process that occurs under strict anaerobic conditions. Soil oxidation - reduction (redox) characteristics are the key soil parameters that control CH₄ production.

Laboratory incubation studies were conducted using 10 wetland rice soils from the Philippines to measure patterns of soil reduction upon wetting. The following logarithmic function was used to quantify soil reduction patterns of soil redox potentials (Eh):

$$y = a + b \ln x$$

where y = Eh at a given time, a = equilibrium Eh for the system, b = rate of reduction, and x = days after flooding.

The reduction capacity of the soil was defined as the difference between the fitted initial Eh and equilibrium Eh values. (See Figure 1 for the fitted and observed Eh values for the soils). Given the excellent description of Eh, the fitted data were used in subsequent analysis. The rate and capacity of soil on wetting strongly influenced CH₄ production (Fig. 2).

The C-N ratio of labile organic matter controlled the reduction rate upon

1. Measured soil redox potentials (Eh, mV) compared with fitted values obtained using a logarithmic function.

wetting, whereas the reduction capacity of the soils was negatively correlated to the active iron, cation exchange capacity, and clay, silt, and sand content.

Predicting CH₄ production upon wetting depends on the rate and capacity for reduction in soils when melted. Initial results suggest that the nature of labile organic matter, buffering due to iron compounds, and soil texture control the soil reduction process. ■

2. Methane production (log, µg CH₄/g soil) during a 30-d incubation predicted from the rate and capacity of soil reduction.